

**A COMPARISON OF LIFE SKILL LEVELS BETWEEN
STUDENTS OF EDUCATION FACULTY AND STUDENTS OF
PEDAGOGICAL FORMATION: THE CASE OF
MUSTAFA KEMAL UNIVERSITY, TURKEY***

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Abstract:

In this study, the life skill levels of undergraduate students of Mustafa Kemal University in 2016-2017 academic year were compared to that of students receiving pedagogical formation education in the same term. For this purpose, 75 students receiving pedagogical formation training and 242 undergraduate students, total of 317 students participated in the research. The life skill levels of students were determined by using Life Skills Scale comprising 5 factors, the groups were compared in terms of each factor and total points. Also analysis of gender, age, marital status of parents, the location at which most of the lifespan covered were used as variables to evaluate the change in life skills level, then the groups were compared according to the findings. According to the Descriptive Statistics, ANOVA, Independent Groups t Test results that are evaluated through the obtained data; the "Life Skills", "Skills of Overcoming Emotions and Stress", "Empathy Establishment and Self-awareness Skills", "Decision-making and Problem solving Skills" "Creative and Critical Thinking Skills" "Communication and Interpersonal Relations Skills" of pedagogical formation students were found to be significantly higher than that of undergraduate students. Besides, it was seen that life skill levels of both groups do not vary with gender, and while the age variable was not functional in the life skill levels of formation students, it was influential in the life skill levels of undergraduate students. The marital status of parents (divorced parents) had significant effect on undergraduate students and no

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significant effect on pedagogical formation students, the place where most of the lifespan was covered had no significant effect on the life skill levels of both groups of students.

Keywords: training teachers, life skills, stress, awareness, empathy

1. Introduction

Technological and scientific improvements of our age has begun changing the society from its roots and societies now turn into information societies. From the industrial society where the industry is prominent to the information society where technology and science is more obvious, production methods, relationships, communication, social structure, values and business environment have changed (Yamaç, 2009). The society expects individuals to develop creative ideas instead of physical labour, produce technological devices that are rapidly changing and emerging; in other words the society expects the development of new skills (Çoban, 1997).

As an educational institution, school helps the learners to develop skills pertaining to different fields apart from providing education. When this educational concept of information and skills form a completion within the individual, it composes life skills for that individual to be utilized throughout one's entire life. Since life skills carry importance for people of all ages, in the development of life skills on school environment, teachers and teacher candidates must have some qualities of certain life skills (Bolat & Balaman, 2017).

Nowadays, in order for a nation to grow economically and not to be beaten by rivals in the competition, the education of life skills would be offered to its citizens; the acquirement of new skills especially in the adulthood period is observed to be an important factor contributing to the economy. Therefore, education of adults is on the agenda of many leaders of countries (Knag, O-Mahony & Peng, 2012).

These changes on the individuals as the society transforms generates new life skills expectations. As the new society form alters, life skills define wise decision-making, effective communication, development of self-management skills, efficient and health life and emotional, social, and interpersonal skills (Mohammadzadeh, Awang & Tajik, 2017; Vaidya, 2014). Similarly WHO states that life skill is defined as the behavioral skill that evaluates the daily requests and difficulties of the individuals. Life skills are described as the necessary abilities to overcome the daily requirements and challenges (Hodge & Danish, 1999). The most general definition of life skill would be the set of abilities and tools that are needed for individuals to succeed in their adult lives. Some examples include teamwork, targeting, leadership and communication skills. Such life skills can be seen as individual funds that improve educational states of youngsters, life qualities and economical prosperity in their future lives (Bailey, Jaggars & Scott-Clayton, 2013). Among the abilities of life skills, the skills of reading discontinuous texts such as map reading, job applications, and timesheet exist (Satherley, Lawes & Sok 2008). These necessary skills were called functional literacy in

the industrial societies and this concept refers to the general skills needed in daily lives apart from abilities of mathematics and usual literacy. Wiederholt interpreted this concept to define the skills of using mathematics and learning literacy in order to live independently (Cronin, Brady & Hult, 2000).

Teaching life skills requires the related factors to be distributed in the educational programme. The best way to implement this is to reveal the situations of real life to the students. That is the only way to make students gain life skills in the 12 year lasting long education. Life skills are taught best when they are served in relationship with the daily life. For instance, the toy advertisements on newspapers might be shown the students for discussion and thus media literacy can be taught (Lewis & Taymans, 1992). However, the education of life skills should be an action that is ever lasting. All of the skills transferred through the education should be related and not repeated. Life skills should be conducted through real life experiences (Cronin, Lord & Wendling, 1991).

Also some studies state that student centered approaches such as cooperative learning contribute to the improvement of life skills of teamwork, communication, social skills, leadership problem solving and decision-making (Smither & Zhu, 2011). Physical education is an appropriate tool for developing life skills. Because it includes interaction, socialization and emotional activities (Kolovelonis, Goudas & Dermitzaki, 2010).

In the education programmes of life skills, self management and social abilities should be the priorities. Self management skill is one of the most important life skills. Self management skill includes self control against the cases of decision-making, problem solving, definition, analysis, resistance to the effect of media, stress and fear. It also gives students the chance to design their self development (Griffin, Botvin, Nichols & Doyle, 2003).

Social skills component consists of abilities related to overcoming shyness, learning how to receive and make praises, how to initiate social interactions, historical relationships and assertiveness. Specially designed materials can be utilized to develop interpersonal abilities (Griffin, Botvin, Scheier, Epstein & Doyle, 2002). In addition to that, there is a positive correlation between health and education. Individuals with enhanced life skills were observed to develop basic skills of health literacy and personal cleaning (Nielsen-Bohlman, Panzer, & Kindig, 2004).

Education of life skills not only affect children but also impact on adults favorably. With the help of life skills education, prevention of some highly risky behaviors such as suicide, assault with various weapons or using dangerous substances was seen to be successful (Hamburg & Takanishi, 1989). Moreover, similar studies showed that life skill education programmes that were provided to the people who had committed offenses resulted in positive changes and the adults receiving this education had less tendency towards re-committing offenses (Adams & Roopnarine, 1994). Life skills offered to adults are mainly towards communication, anger management, career management, targeting, business skills, time management, relationship management, budget management and dangers of using substances (Melton & Pennel, 1998).

World Health Organization [WHO] has signified multiple life skills of a healthy person. Some of these skills refer to the ceratin situations whereas some of them have general properties. 10 main skill sets were formed to lay foundation for many cultures and encourage the psychological health of the individual (Sreekumar, 2016; Bolat & Balaman, 2017). These are; decision-making skills, problem solving skills, emphaty establishment skills, self awareness skills, communication skills, interpersonal communication skills, overcoming the emotions skills, overcoming stress skills, skills of creative thinking and skills of critical thinking (WHO, 1997).

Table 1: Main Categories of Life Skills

Decision making and problem solving	Creative and critical thinking	Communication and interpersonal Communication	Self awareness and emphaty	Overcoming stress and emotions
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Individuals who have the decision-making ability can make inferences about the beginning and the end of the process. The result is the point where suspicions and argument come to an end, chosen element is applied logically. Decision-making is the act of chosing the influential option among the choices (Kurt, 2003; Pujar & Patil, 2016; Bolat & Balaman, 2017).

Conceptually problem solving requires the individual to perceive the information, take it through a process and utilize it (Abaan & Altntoprak, 2005). This ability the individual possesses provides him to cope constructively with the problems in his life. Unresolved problems can lead to significant mental stress and physical stress (WHO, 1997, Sreekumar, 2016). This situation explains the requirement of problem-solving skills for the individual (Bolat & Balaman, 2017).

The ability to develop empathy helps us to understand the different people, social environment and situations that are different from ourselves. In this context, a prospective teacher must have the ability to empathize in order to understand the different student characters, and their emotions and problems. This skill, that makes ourselves known constitutes the precondition for effective communication and interpersonal communication skills (WHO, 1997; Sreekumar, 2016; Pujar & Patil, 2016). Prospective teachers with self-awareness skill who recognize themselves at a sufficient level can create awareness through in professional means. They may become open to self-development by recognizing their weak and strength characteristics (Bolat & Balaman, 2017).

Individuals whose communication skills developed can cope more healthily with the problems they face. As it is known that effective teaching cannot be achieved without communication, it is important for the success of the educational processes if and to the extent prospective teachers are equipped with communication skills. As it is known that school and more specifically classroom is the professional communication environment of a teacher or prospective teacher, the ability of the teacher to communicate with his students and colleagues in interpersonal communication will

have an impact on his professional achievement and professional awareness in his profession (Bolat & Balaman, 2017).

Emotions affect all the individuals with positive and negative effects. It seems possible that we can say that the ability to cope with emotions has improved in individuals who have the ability to identify and regulate these causes. Overcoming the stress is the whole of the efforts of the individual to adapt to stressful situations. Individuals and prospective teachers with this skill can cope with stress and use stress as a tool to increase motivation.

Creative thinking as a process is associated with the process of problem-solving. Prospective teachers with creative thinking skills have high level ability to cope with professional problems. In addition to this, the creativity traits of the individuals that they train will develop at a positive level. Critical thinking helps us to identify a wide range of subjective analyzes of objective data and helps us to evaluate how well each analysis can respond to our needs (Coughan, 2007). In addition to the application of new situations and the development of assessment skills, critical thinking helps us to make sense of values and attitudes. As these features of critical thinking are considered, the fact that prospective teachers have this skill area provides important advantages in evaluating and transferring knowledge. For this reason, the fact that prospective teachers have the life skills explained in advance will contribute to their professional work in the context of teacher competencies.

1.1 Purpose of the Study

In this study, it is purposed to compare the level of life skills of students who received pedagogical formation education and of undergraduate students who have received teaching profession in the same period with different variables. The lack of research on prospective teachers' life skills in the teacher education literature indicates the importance of this study.

2. Method

The research is survey model from quantitative research methods. As is known, survey models are carried out in natural conditions, without any modification in order to bring out a certain situation in a specific subject (Karasar, 2015).

2.1. Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of a total of 2971 student, including 627 pedagogical formation students and 2344 undergraduate students studying at Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Education in 2016- 2017 academic year. The sample consisted of a total of 317 students, including 75 pedagogical formation students and 242 undergraduate students who were selected by means of purposive sampling method among the students in the school.

2.2. Data Collection Tool

The Life Skills Questionnaire (LSQ) developed by Bolat and Balaman (2017) with a reliability coefficient of 0.90, was used to determine the life skill levels of the students. Scale consists of 5 factors. These are 'Coping Skills with Stress and Emotions (CSSE) ($\alpha=0,82$)', 'Empathy and Self-Awareness Skills (ESAS) ($\alpha=0,82$)', 'Decision Making and Problem-Solving Skills (DMPSS) ($\alpha=0,72$)', 'Creative Thinking and Critical Thinking Skills (CTCTS) ($\alpha=0,73$)' and 'Communication and Interpersonal Relationship Skills (CIRS) ($\alpha=0,66$)'.

2.3. Analysis of Data

Data obtained from the Life Skills Scale were entered into the SPSS 22 program and analyzed using this software. Descriptive statistics include average ($\bar{X}$), standard deviation (SD), maximum value (Max), minimum value (Min), coefficient of skewness (CS), coefficient of kurtosis (CK). Compliance of the data to parametric tests was analyzed by normal distribution of data (with skewness and kurtosis coefficients) and homogeneity of variances (Levene's Test).

- Descriptive statistics were used to examine the groups in terms of demographic variables and to test the compliance of level of life skills of the undergraduate and formation students and the scores obtained from the factors.
- Independent Groups t Test was used to determine whether students' total scores of life skill levels and scores obtained from the factors varied according to the level of education (undergraduate / formation).
- Independent Groups t Test was used to determine whether the life skills of the undergraduate and formation students varied according to gender.
- ANOVA has been observed to determine whether the life skills of the undergraduate and formation students varied according to age, parental status and place of resident.

3. Findings

When the suitability of the obtained data to parametric tests is analyzed, it is assumed that the skewness and kurtosis coefficients are in the appropriate range for parametric tests, that Levene's Test is also meaningful and therefore the variances are homogeneous. For this reason, parametric tests were applied with data.

3.1. Findings Related to Total Points

According to descriptive statistical results in terms of scale factors and life skills total scores of 75 formation students included in the study:

Table 2: Descriptive statistical results of formation students

	Max.	Min.	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	C.S.	C.K.
CSSE	35	9	26,57	6,61	-0,60	-0,19
ESAS	35	19	29,13	4,10	-0,15	-0,85
DMPSS	35	20	29,97	4,27	-0,68	-0,40
CTCTS	25	10	21,33	3,23	-0,73	0,52
CIRS	20	8	16,76	2,59	-0,76	-0,48
LSS	150	80	123,77	18,06	-0,30	-0,66

In terms of factors, it is seen that DMPSS factor has the highest average ($\bar{X} = 29,97$) and CIRS factor has the lowest average ($\bar{X} = 16,76$) and C.S. and C.K. values are within ± 1 range). According to descriptive statistical results in terms of scale factors and whole scale of 242 undergraduate students;

Table 3: Descriptive statistical results of undergraduate students

	Max.	Min.	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	C.S.	C.K.
CSSE	31	7	20,67	4,38	-0,59	0,20
ESAS	35	15	25,47	3,23	-0,25	0,31
DMPSS	33	18	25,90	2,68	-0,05	0,23
CTCTS	24	12	18,17	2,33	-0,10	-0,04
CIRS	20	6	15,07	2,36	-0,50	1,14
LSS	125	81	105,28	8,75	-0,52	-0,03

In terms of factors, it is observed that the highest factor is DMPSS factor ($\bar{X} = 25,90$) and the lowest average factor is CIRS factor ($\bar{X} = 15,07$) as it is in undergraduate students.

3.2. Findings Related to Comparison of Groups

Life skills of undergraduate and formation students were compared in terms of scale dimensions and total scale scores. When the groups were compared in terms of their life skills level total scores;

Table 4: Comparison of life skills level total scores of undergraduate and formation students

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Undergraduate	242	105,27	8,76	-12,02	0,00*
Formation	75	123,77	18,06		

*p<0,05

The total scores of the students' life skill level varies according to the level of education. The life skill levels of the students of the formation were significantly higher than those of the undergraduate students ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). When the groups were compared in terms of the scores obtained from the factor CSSE;

Table 5: Comparison of groups in terms of factor CSSE

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Undergraduate	242	20,67	4,38	-8,93	0,00*
Formation	75	26,57	6,61		

*p<0,05

In terms of factor CSSE, which is a sub-factor of life skills, the average of CSSE factor scores of formation students was significantly higher than that of undergraduate students ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). When the groups were compared in terms of the scores obtained from ESAS factor;

Table 6: Comparison of groups in terms of factor ESAS

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Undergraduate	242	25,47	3,23	-8,01	0,00*
Formation	75	29,13	4,10		

*p<0,05

In terms of ESAS sub-factor, the average of formation students is significantly higher than the average of undergraduate students ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). When the groups were compared in terms of the scores obtained from the factor DMPSS;

Table 7: Comparison of groups in terms of DMPSS factor

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Undergraduate	242	25,90	2,68	-9,83	0,00*
Formation	75	29,97	4,27		

*p<0,05

It is seen that the average of formation students in terms of DMPSS sub-factor is significantly higher than the average of undergraduate students ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). When the groups were compared in terms of the scores obtained from CTCTS factor;

Table 8: Comparison of groups in terms of CTCTS factor

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Undergraduate	242	18,17	2,33	-9,30	0,00*
Formation	75	21,33	3,23		

*p<0,05

In terms of CTCTS sub-factor, the average of formation students is significantly higher than the average of undergraduate students ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). When the groups were compared in terms of the scores obtained from CIRS factor;

Table 9: Comparison of groups in terms of factor CIRS

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Undergraduate	242	15,07	2,36	-5,28	0,00*
Formation	75	16,76	2,59		

*p<0,05

In terms of sub-factor CIRS, the average of formation students is significantly higher than the average of undergraduate students ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$).

3.3. Results Related to Gender

According to the Independent Groups t Test, which was conducted to determine whether the life skill levels of undergraduate students changed according to gender;

Table 10: Comparison of life skill levels of undergraduate students in terms of gender

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Female	168	105,52	8,72	0,62	0,53
Male	74	104,75	8,87		

As the life skill level score of the undergraduate students was grouped according to gender, the average scores of women were higher than the average scores of men, but this difference was not significant ($p = 0.53 > 0.05$).

According to the Independent Groups t Test, which was conducted to determine whether the life skill levels of the formation students changed according to the gender;

Table 11: Comparison of life skill levels of formation students in terms of gender

Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	t	p
Female	23	123,65	20,41	-0,03	0,97
Male	52	123,83	17,14		

As the life skills level score of the formation students were grouped according to sex, mean scores of women were higher than male average scores but this difference was not significant ($p = 0.97 > 0.05$).

3.4. Age Related Findings

According to variance analysis (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life skill levels of the formation students changed according to age;

Table 12: Comparison of life skill levels of formation students according to age

Age Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	p
21 years	7	116,86	17,01	0,38
22 years	7	120,71	12,95	
23 years and over	61	124,92	18,67	

It is understood that there are no 18, 19, 20 age students in the age group, whereas the formation students are gathered in 21, 22, 23 and over age groups. However, the life skills of the students in the formation do not change according to age ($p = 0.38 > 0.05$).

According to variance analysis (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life skill levels of undergraduate students change according to age;

Table 13: Comparison of life skill levels of undergraduate students according to age

Age Group	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	p
18 years	14	105,07	6,23	0,00*
19 years	46	103,37	8,44	
20 years	74	103,81	7,73	
21 years	52	103,93	9,03	
22 years	24	108,74	10,12	
23 years and over	32	111,15	8,18	

There are undergraduates in all age options and the life skills of undergraduate students vary according to age ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$). According to the results of LSD which is conducted to determine statistically significant difference among which groups;

Table 14: LSD analysis results of life skill levels of undergraduate students according to age

Age Group	18	19	20	21	22	23
18 years	-					
19 years	0,51	-				
20 years	0,60	0,78	-			
21 years	0,65	0,74	0,93	-		
22 years	0,19	0,01*	0,01*	0,02*	-	
23 years and over	0,02*	0,00*	0,00*	0,00*	0,29	-

- Between the age of 18 and 23 years of age or older, on behalf of the 23 years and over;
- Between the ages of 19 and 22, on behalf of the 22-year-old;
- Between the ages of 19 and 23 years of age and older, on behalf of the 23 years and over;
- Between the ages of 20 and 22, on behalf of the 22-year-old;
- Between the ages of 20 and 23 years of age and older, on behalf of the 23 years and over;
- Between the age of 21 and 22 years, on behalf of the 22-year-old;
- Between the age of 21 and the age of 23 years and over, on behalf of the 23 years and over; it is understood that there are statistically significant differences.

3.5. Findings Related to Parental Status

According to analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether life skill levels of undergraduate students vary according to whether parents are together or not;

Table 15: Comparisons of life skill levels of undergraduates compared to the parental status

Parental Status	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	p
Together	229	105,49	8,63	
Married but living separately	5	95,24	12,87	0,03*
Divorced	8	105,63	6,55	

It is seen that the level of life skills of undergraduates varies according to whether the parents are together or separated ($p = 0,03 < 0,05$). According to the results of LSD to determine which groups mean difference between the averages;

Table 16: LSD analysis results of life skills of undergraduate students according to whether parents are together

Parental Status	Together	Married but living separately	Divorced
Together	-		
Married but living separately	0,01*	-	
Divorced	0,96	0,03*	-

According to LSD results; between the together and married but living separately, there is result on the behalf of the married but living separately. Between the married but living separately and divorced, there is result on the behalf of the divorced. It was understood that there were statistically significant differences between the groups of parental status. According to analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life skills of the students of the formation vary according to whether the parents are together or not;

Table 17: Comparisons of life skill levels of formation students compared to parental status

Parental Status	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	p
Together	70	123,76	18,12	
Married but living separately	2	111,00	16,97	0,42
Divorced	3	132,67	17,89	

It is understood that the life skill level of the formation students did not change according to whether the parents were together or separated ($p = 0,42 > 0,05$).

3.6. Findings Related to the Variable of Place of Residence

According to variance analysis (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life skill levels of the undergraduate students vary according to the variable of the students' place of residence;

Table 18: Changes in the level of life skills of undergraduates depending on where they live

Place of Residence	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	p
In village and rural settlement	32	105,78	10,37	
In town or county	65	106,98	8,52	
In city	101	104,49	7,83	0,22
In metropolis	42	103,86	9,78	
Somewhere abroad	2	112,00	4,24	

According to the table, it is seen that the level of life skills of undergraduate students did not change according to the variable that is place of residence ($p > 0.05$). According to variance analysis (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether the life skill levels of the students of the formation have changed according to the variable that is place of residence;

Table 19: Change in the level of life skills of formation students according to the place of residence

Place of Residence	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	p
In village or rural settlement	11	112,18	17,77	
In town or county	19	122,74	18,78	
In city	31	125,55	16,89	0,07
In metropolis	14	130,36	17,28	
Somewhere abroad	-	-	-	

According to the table, it is understood that the life skill level of the formation students did not change according to the variable where their life was spent ($p > 0.05$).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, the level of life skills of students who received pedagogical formation education in the same period as the undergraduate students who received teaching profession education were compared with different variables. Several results related to research have been reached with the comparisons.

The life skills of the formation students are significantly higher than the life skills of the undergraduate students. Average scores of "Empathy and Self-Awareness Skills" factor score, "Decision Making and Problem-Solving Skills" factor average scores, CTCTS factor score average, "Creative Thinking and Critical Thinking" Skills "factor scores and" Communication Interpersonal Skills "factor scores were found to be significantly higher in the formation students than undergraduate students. This does not mean that the students of the formation have full life skills, but it does not mean that undergraduate students do not have these skills. It should not be forgotten that life skills can be improved. Pujar and Patil (2016) conducted a study on the life skills in the 13-15 age group and found that these students who received education on life skills developed skills such as problem solving and stress coping. Similarly, there are studies that suggest that life skills training for young adults may be influential on several factors (Vranda & Rao, 2011; Sreekumar, 2016; İşmen Gazioğlu & Canel, 2015). Similarly, Altıntaş and Özdemir (2014) have state that students' creative thinking skills can be improved through differentiation approach in their experimental studies. Social skills must consist of the ability of individuals to come from above shyness, understand how praise will be given, initiate social interactions, history associations and assertiveness. Specially designed materials can be used to help improve interpersonal skills (Griffin, Botvin, Scheier, Epstein, & Doyle, 2002).

Life skills scores of undergraduate and formation students do not change according to gender. Life skills focus primarily on self-management and social skills in educational programs. Self-management skills are one of the most important elements of life skills. Self-management involves self-control over situations such as decision making, problem solving, identification, analysis, resistance to media influence, anxiety and fear. It also allows students to design their own development (Griffin, Botvin, Nichols. & Doyle, 2003). However, gender variance is a factor to be considered. It is important to remember that gender roles are different in social life, and that life skills will vary according to this.

The life skill levels of undergraduate students have changed according to their age. Age differences have generally been found to favor the older age group. This can be interpreted as an increase in the life skills of individuals as their age progresses. Because the frequency of life skills in social life is a reality that can cope with problems, solve problems, make decisions and improve communication skills. Bailey, Jaggar and Scott-Clayton (2013) argue that life skills should be seen as individual capital that enhances young people's educational status, quality of life, and future economic well-being. It is an approach that supports the importance of life skills.

The level of life skills of undergraduates varies according to whether the parents are together or separated. Statistically significant difference is stated in favor of the married but living separately contrary to living together. Also, statistically significant difference is stated between the married but living separately and divorced in favor of the divorced. However, it was concluded that the life skill levels of the formation students did not vary according to whether the parents are together or separated. Life skills education should not only be directed towards children but also to children's families. This training can be a positive contribution to the perspective of parents. Many studies suggest that parents should be given a general education on the teaching of life skills. Roessler, Loyd and Brolin (1990) and Vasa and Steckelberg (1980) have succeeded in teaching parents the concepts of life skills; so that parents can better exemplify their daily life with their children and contribute to the development of the life skills of the students. Counseling and assisting parents with both structured and unstructured activities at home will (a) increase their awareness of their parents' daily life skills, (b) focus on increasing the child's independence as much as possible, and (c) increases positive interactions between child and parents.

The level of life skills of undergraduate and formation students does not vary according to where they live their lives. Tekin and Ehtiyar (2010) conducted a study of hotel managers and stated that managers are not affected by demographic variables in decision making skills, and generally the intuitive decision-making style is effective in decision making. In this study, it can be said that the situation determined for both groups has similar results with the work conducted by Tekin and Ehtiyar (2010).

5. Suggestions

In this study, the level of life skills of students who received pedagogical formation education compared to undergraduate students who received teaching profession education were compared with different variables. The most important result that should be considered in the research is that the students who receive formation training have higher level of life skills in many areas than the teacher candidates trained at undergraduate level. New investigations may be conducted to determine the exact cause of this condition.

Teaching programs, lessons or courses that improve the life skills of prospective teachers in undergraduate teacher training programs can be organized.

Apart from the teacher candidates, the life skills of the teachers who have participated in the workforce can be determined. According to the results of the research, teachers can gain life skills with the help of in-service trainings.

The life skills that will be gained to teacher candidates in the education process must be determined in the context of teacher competencies. Life skills can be determined by considering individual and social expectations. Thus, the importance of life skills in teacher education can be improved.

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